

Supplementary Materials for “Direct Forcing of the Collisional Auroral Ionosphere by Kinetic Alfvén Turbulence”

Magnus F Ivarsen,* Jean-Pierre St-Maurice,† Brian Pitzel, Saif Marei, and Glenn C Hussey
Department of Physics and Engineering Physics, University of Saskatchewan, Saskatoon, Canada

Kaili Song and P. T. Jayachandran
Physics Department, University of New Brunswick, Fredericton, Canada

Luca Spogli
Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, Rome, Italy

Devin R Huyghebaert‡
Leibniz Institute of Atmospheric Physics, Kühlungsborn, Germany

Yangyang Shen
Department of Earth and Space Sciences, University of California, Los Angeles, USA

Satoshi Kasahara and Kunihiro Keika
Department of Earth and Planetary Science, University of Tokyo, Tokyo, Japan

Yoshizumi Miyoshi and Tomo Hori
Institute for Space-Earth Environmental Research, Nagoya University, Nagoya, Japan

David R Themens
School of Engineering, University of Birmingham, Birmingham, UK

Yoichi Kazama and Shiang-Yu Wang
Academia Sinica Institute of Astronomy and Astrophysics, Taipei, Taiwan

Ayako Matsuoka
Data Analysis Center for Geomagnetism and Space Magnetism, Kyoto University, Kyoto, Japan

Iku Shinohara and Takefumi Mitani
Institute of Space and Astronautical Science, Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency, Sagami, Japan

Shoichiro Yokota
Department of Earth and Space Science, Osaka University, Toyonaka, Japan

This document contains a detailed description of the instrumentation, data, and analysis techniques applied in the the paper “Direct Forcing of the Collisional Auroral Ionosphere by Kinetic Alfvén Turbulence”, referred to as the Main Paper. We likewise provide a detailed theoretical foundation for the D-region ‘chemical etching’ processes that we evoke to explain such low-altitude turbulence observations.

I: INTRODUCTION

This document supports the findings of the Main Paper, by providing technical, theoretical, and observational details concerning the many multi-instrumental conjunctions that we analyze, detailing the data analysis techniques that we have applied, and we also provide a a theoretical foundation for the chemical etching mech-

anism that we evoke to explain low-altitude (< 90 km) HF echoes.

The document is organized as follows. Section II (Figure S1) describes the core dataset used in the Main Paper, namely the ten ground-ground conjunctions between the experimental HF radar ICEBEAR and the Rabbit Lake GPS receiver in the CHAIN network of ionospheric scintillation monitoring receivers (ISMRS). Section III (Fig-

Figure S 1. Six simultaneous ground-ground conjunctions between the ICEBEAR radar and observations from the CHAIN ISMR in Rabbit Lake. Each panel compares the spectral density measurements, the internal structure of the radar point-clouds denoted by a black line and the spectrum of GPS amplitude fluctuations in red and gray colors. The spectral indices are calculated automatically following Ref. [1] and are indicated, as is the Fresnel-scale.

ure S2) describes an extended space-ground-ground conjunction between ICEBEAR, CHAIN, and two European Swarm satellites. Section IV (Figures S3, S4) describes a total of ten conjunctions between ICEBEAR and the Japanese spacecraft Arase, of which one includes observations from CHAIN. Finally, Section V provides a detailed theoretical foundation for the chemical etching mechanism, supported by the analysis of an ICEBEAR-Arase conjunction (Figure S5).

II: TEN ICEBEAR-CHAIN CONJUNCTIONS

Figure S1 showcases six simultaneous ICEBEAR-CHAIN conjunctions, occurring in rapid succession during two extended events that took place on 7 July 2023 and 18 August 2022. Each panel of Figure S1 shows the composite powerspectrum for each conjunction event. We normalize the power amplitude to facilitate a direct spectral shape comparison, and we apply an automatic spectral slope- & break-point detection algorithm based on piecewise linear Hermite polynomials [4], with close details described in, e.g., Ref. [1] and Ref. [5]. For scale-sizes between 750 m and 3000 m the spectral shapes from the

Figure S 2. Two space-ground-ground conjunctions, and one ground-ground-conjunction, between ICEBEAR, a CHAIN ISMR, and the Swarm A and C satellites, on 6 May 2023. Panel b) shows the spatial distribution of echoes (black point-cloud), with the Swarm satellite orbits (blue lines) and GPS pierce-point (red circle) superposed. Panels a) and f) show the magnitude of the perpendicular magnetic fluctuations observed by the Swarm satellites (black line and blue colorscale), with the latitudinal distribution of ICEBEAR echoes superposed in red. Panels b,d,e, and g) show various composite powerspectra, with ICEBEAR clustering spectra (black), compared to textschain k -spectra (red, gray) and field-aligned current structuring spectra (blue) measured by Swarm. Panel e) shows an enlarged portion of the composite ICEBEAR-CHAIN spectrum in panel d).

two different methods are observed to match strikingly well. What is more, the steep slopes at the larger scales (> 1 km) are highly consistent with the steep slopes seen at smaller scales (< 100 m), with observed spectral index values between -2.6 and -3.1 . A prominent break-point is observed near the Fresnel-scale, and similar prominent features are visible at scale-sizes around 1–10 km, both in accordance with expectations based on plasma instabilities from the literature [6–11].

The remaining four composite spectra that we analyze are presented in Figures 2, 3, and 6 in the Main Paper.

III: EXTENDED ICEBEAR-CHAIN-SWARM CONJUNCTION

We shall describe two successive space-ground-ground conjunctions that offer a clear, physical interpretation of the composite spectra. Figure S2 details two triple conjunctions between ICEBEAR, CHAIN, and the European Space Agency’s Swarm mission [12, 13], consisting of three polar orbiting satellites (inclination 87° , altitude ~ 450 km, and orbital period of 90 minutes).

The conjunctions, with their geospatial coordinates detailed in Figure S2c), exhibited very strong magnetic fluctuations perpendicular to Earth’s magnetic field, produced by field-aligned currents, and what follows is a

Figure S 3. A space-ground-ground conjunction between ICEBEAR, CHAIN, and the Japanese inner magnetosphere spacecraft Arase that took place on 2 August 2023. **Panels a,b)** show the satellite location in the magnetosphere, while **Panel c)** shows the geospatial distribution of radar echoes, with Arase’s northern hemisphere orbital footprint in green dashed lines (using the Tsy04 mapping method [2]) and the GPS pierce-point as a red cross, all using the AACGM coordinate system mapped along Earth’s magnetic field-lines [3]. The conjunction is detailed in Figure 2d–g) in the Main Paper.

treatment of the structure, or *filamentation*, of those currents.

Following Ref. [14] and Ref. [15], we Fourier analyze the Swarm 50 Hz magnetic field fluctuations transformed into a mean-field-aligned coordinate system [16, 17], and this Fourier analysis yields information on electrical current filamentation, the degree to which the observed currents are non-laminar, or anomalous. The quantity is analogous to the structuring of magnetic field-tubes in the plane perpendicular to the geomagnetic field. Figure S2a, f) detail the observed magnitude of the perpendicular magnetic fluctuations, with the distribution of simultaneously observed ICEBEAR echoes superposed with a red line.

As the Swarm satellites orbit through the topside (F-region) ionosphere with a velocity of $v_s = 7.62$ km/s, we apply Taylor’s “frozen-in”-hypothesis to convert the temporal powerspectra to k -spectra. These are superposed on the ICEBEAR echo clustering spectra in Figure S2b, g), showing reasonably good agreement on a wide range of spatial scales between 10^5 m and 750 m (below 750 m, the Swarm spectra drop off, indicating an effective Nyquist frequency of 12.5 Hz for the Swarm magnetic field instrument). We note a very good shape-wise agreement

between the radar clustering spectra and the observed field-aligned current structuring, echoing recent studies [14, 15]. The implications are that the spatial characteristics of turbulence in the E-region are contained, or communicated, by filaments in the field-aligned currents.

In Figure S2d, e), we compare the ICEBEAR and GPS spectra, for which the simultaneous conjunction took place between the two satellites’ orbit, and which again exhibit excellent shape-wise agreement down to individual spectral features around 1 kilometer (inset panel e).

IV: NINE ICEBEAR-ARASE CONJUNCTIONS

On 2 August 2023, an extended conjunction took place between ICEBEAR and the Japanese inner magnetosphere satellite Arase. During this conjunction, two additional ICEBEAR–CHAIN conjunctions took place. Results from this events are presented in Figure 2d–g) in the Main Paper. What follows is an overview of the geospatial locations of the various instruments during this event.

Arase orbits Earth at a maximum distance (semi-major axis) of around 5 Earth radii, with a magnetospheric orbit that keeps the satellite relatively close to equator with an ionospheric footprint that routinely sample auroral latitudes [21]: it has an apogee of 32,000 km and a perigee of 400 km, an inclination angle of 31° , and a period of 570 minutes. The satellite’s orbit in the magnetosphere is shown in Figure S3a, b), while its ionospheric footprint is shown with a dashed line in Figure S3c). The satellite was located some 19° equatorward of magnetospheric equator, and it was observing a considerable flux of electrons with pitch angles lower than or equal to 5° . Figure 2e, f) in the Main Paper present these observations. The observed flux of particles is a proxy of the real precipitating particle flux [22], producing the characteristic diffuse aurora that we infer to have occurred during the event.

Next, Figure S4 shows seven conjunctions between ICEBEAR and Arase, akin to Figure 1 in the Main Paper, where we use the foregoing analysis to infer ionization curves (green profile), and compare those curves to the altitude distribution of HF echoes (black profiles). For each conjunction event, we confirm the geospatial proximity of Arase’s northern hemisphere footprint with the distribution of HF echoes, and we show the total, observed energy flux observed by Arase in inset panels.

Figure 4 is a unique dataset of low-altitude HF echoes coincident with highly energetic particle precipitation, and in the next section we provide a new theoretical foundation to explain low (< 90 km) plasma turbulence observations.

Figure S 4. Seven space-ground conjunctions between ICEBEAR and Arase, showing altitude profiles of precipitation-induced ionization rate (green profiles) and the altitude distribution of HF echoes (black profiles). Inset plots show the combined precipitating electron energy flux through the LEP-e [18], MEP-e [19], and HEP [20] instruments onboard Arase.

V: THE DRIVEN-DISSIPATIVE PHOTOCHEMICAL FORCING: “CHEMICAL ETCHING”

The persistence of fine-scale plasma density structures (< 10 m) in the highly collisional D-region (< 90 km) presents a fundamental challenge to classical diffusion theory. Building on the thermal attachment instability framework identified in artificial heating experiments [23], we identify driven-dissipative photochemical forcing as the primary structuring mechanism. This mechanism exploits the dominance of rapid electron attachment to neutrals (formation of negative ions) in D-region loss processes.

The evolution of an electron density perturbation δN_e is governed by the continuity equation coupled with the electron energy equation, where the linearized loss term L is determined by the attachment frequency ν_{att} [24, 25],

$$\frac{\partial(\delta N_e)}{\partial t} \approx - \left(\frac{\partial \nu_{att}}{\partial T_e} \delta T_e \right) N_e - D_a \nabla^2 (\delta N_e), \quad (1)$$

where D_a is the ambipolar diffusion coefficient and T_e is the electron temperature. In this note, we describe the

conditions when the loss mechanism,

$$\tau_{chem} \approx \left(\frac{\partial \nu_{att}}{\partial T_e} \delta T_e \right)^{-1} \approx \frac{1}{\nu_{att}^{eff}}, \quad (2)$$

works faster than the smoothing mechanism,

$$\tau_{diff} \approx \frac{1}{k^2 D_a}. \quad (3)$$

Crucially, we invoke a “pre-conditioned” non-equilibrium neutral background, provided by broadband energetic electron precipitation (1 keV–100 keV, with a tail exceeding 600 keV). This precipitation functions as a ‘seedbed,’ sustaining a high population of vibrationally excited oxygen $O_2(v)$ and metastable $O_2(a^1\Delta_g)$ via impact excitation and cascade by secondary electrons [26].

While Alfvén wave absorption elevates T_e , the increase is insufficient to drive dissociative attachment to ground-state oxygen (threshold ~ 3.7 eV). However, for the vibrationally excited population $O_2(v)$, the reaction threshold effectively vanishes. As v increases, the neutral wave function overlaps favorably with the repulsive potential curve of the negative ion (O_2^-) [27]. For

$O_2(v \geq 10)$ or $O_2(a^1\Delta_g)$, the peak cross-section increases by factors of 10^2 to 10^3 . Consequently, a modest rise in plasma temperature (e.g., $T_e \sim 0.03$ eV to $T_e \sim 0.1$ eV) broadens the electron Maxwellian distribution sufficiently to access these resonant channels,

The resonant nature of this process causes the attachment frequency ν_{att} to spike instantaneously with T_e , converting mobile free electrons into heavy, slow negative ions.

We can test this quantitatively at 85 km altitude. Using standard atmospheric parameters (NRLMSISE-00) for the background neutral density ($N_n \approx 10^{20} \text{ m}^{-3}$) and ambipolar diffusion ($D_a \approx 4 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$), we compare the timescales for a $\lambda = 3$ m structure (the ICEBEAR backscatter wavelength).

For τ_{chem} , we calculate the effective rate for the resonant channel $e + O_2^* \rightarrow O^- + O$. With excited state densities predicted by precipitation models [26] and resonant rates from [27], the effective attachment frequency during heating spikes to,

$$\nu_{att}^{eff} \approx 10^1 - 10^2 \text{ s}^{-1}. \quad (5)$$

Comparing this to the diffusive smoothing time:

$$\tau_{chem} \approx \frac{1}{\nu_{att}^{eff}} \approx \mathbf{10 \text{ ms}} < \tau_{diff} \approx \frac{1}{k^2 D_a} \approx \mathbf{50 \text{ ms}}. \quad (6)$$

Since $\tau_{chem} < \tau_{diff}$, the chemical 'etching' dominates, allowing fine-scale structures to persist against diffusion.

Validation – The validity of the chemical etching mechanism is supported by experimental measurements of the reaction cross-sections. Ref. [28] confirms that for the metastable $O_2(a^1\Delta_g)$ state, the dissociative attachment cross-section is enhanced by a factor of 3.5 and the energy threshold is shifted lower by 0.98 eV compared to the ground state.

Furthermore, modeling of energetic electron precipitation events (40–100 keV) by Ref. [29] demonstrates the efficient production of these metastable states in the D-region, providing the necessary 'seedbed' density ($[O_2^*] \gtrsim 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-3}$). Finally, while electron impact ionization of metastables is possible [30], the high energy threshold for ionization (> 10 eV) compared to the resonant attachment threshold ensures that plasma loss dominates over production in the range of electron temperatures ($T_e \sim 0.1$ – 0.5 eV) generated by Alfvénic heating.

The 13 March 2021 event – In Figure 1 of the Main Paper, we show an event during which highly energetic electron precipitation observed by Arase coincided with low-altitude HF echoes observed by ICEBEAR, with matching altitude profiles. In Figure S5 we show data

Figure S 5. **Panel a**) shows ICEBEAR echo altitude distribution (red line) superposed on the ionization altitude profile (green line), inferred from the Arase-measured electron precipitation (**panel b**). **Panel c**) shows the HF echoes in an altitude-time-intensity diagram (with colorscale denoting echo signal-to-noise ratio (SNR)), with the peak ionization altitude (\pm one standard deviation) shown in green. **Panel d**) shows a cross-correlation analysis between the echo detection rates and the 60 keV electron flux. **Panel e**) shows time-series of the electron energy fluxes through the three particle detectors (red) and the echo detection rates (black).

from this event, for a 16-minute interval that features 90-second periodic bursts in both energy flux and echo detection rates, corresponding to Pc3-5 (Alfvén) pulsations. While we are not able to measure heating rates, the altitude distributions in Figure 5a) are inconsistent with any existing framework for plasma instabilities, with extant ionization and HF echo detections reaching down to 80 km altitude. The cross-correlation analysis, while not exhibiting strong correlation (correlation coefficients $\rho \approx 0.45$), the signal is clearly identifying a signature in the two timeseries consistent with Alfvénic pumping, consistent with the driven-dissipative photochemical forcing processes outlined in the foregoing.

* Contact: magnus.fagernes@gmail.com; Also at The European Space Agency Centre for Earth Observation, Frascati, Italy

† Also at Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Western Ontario, London, Canada

- [‡] Also at Department of Physics and Engineering Physics, University of Saskatchewan, Saskatoon, Canada
- [1] M. F. Ivarsen, Y. Jin, A. Spicher, and L. B. N. Clausen, Direct Evidence for the Dissipation of Small-Scale Ionospheric Plasma Structures by a Conductive E Region, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics* **124**, 2935 (2019).
 - [2] N. A. Tsyganenko and M. I. Sitnov, Modeling the dynamics of the inner magnetosphere during strong geomagnetic storms, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics* **110**, 2004JA010798 (2005).
 - [3] K. B. Baker and S. Wing, A new magnetic coordinate system for conjugate studies at high latitudes, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics* **94**, 9139 (1989).
 - [4] J. D'Errico, SLM-shape language modeling, SLM-Shape Language Modeling. <http://www.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/24443-slm-shape-language-modeling>: Mathworks (2009).
 - [5] M. F. Ivarsen, J.-P. St-Maurice, Y. Jin, J. Park, W. Miloch, A. Spicher, Y.-S. Kwak, and L. B. N. Clausen, Steepening Plasma Density Spectra in the Ionosphere: The Crucial Role Played by a Strong E-Region, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics* **126**, e2021JA029401 (2021).
 - [6] J. P. Villain, C. Hanuise, and C. Beghin, ARCAD3-SAFARI coordinated study of auroral and polar F-region ionospheric irregularities, *Annales Geophysicae* **4**, 61 (1986).
 - [7] M. F. Ivarsen, J.-P. St-Maurice, G. Hussey, A. Spicher, Y. Jin, A. Lozinsky, L. V. Goodwin, D. Galeschuk, J. Park, and L. B. N. Clausen, Measuring small-scale plasma irregularities in the high-latitude E- and F-regions simultaneously, *Scientific Reports* **13**, 11579 (2023).
 - [8] S. Basu, S. Basu, E. MacKenzie, W. R. Coley, J. R. Sharber, and W. R. Hoegy, Plasma structuring by the gradient drift instability at high latitudes and comparison with velocity shear driven processes, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics* **95**, 7799 (1990).
 - [9] H. Mounir, A. Berthelier, J. C. Cerisier, D. Lagoutte, and C. Beghin, The small-scale turbulent structure of the high latitude ionosphere - Arcad-Aureol-3 observations, *Annales Geophysicae* **9**, 725 (1991).
 - [10] A. Spicher, W. J. Miloch, and J. I. Moen, Direct evidence of double-slope power spectra in the high-latitude ionospheric plasma, *Geophysical Research Letters* **41**, 1406 (2014).
 - [11] A. M. Hamza, K. Song, K. Meziane, and J. P. Thayyil, *Two-Component Phase Scintillation Spectra in the Auroral Region: Observations and Model*, Preprint (Preprints, 2023).
 - [12] E. Friis-Christensen, H. Lühr, and G. Hulot, Swarm: A constellation to study the Earth's magnetic field, *Earth, Planets and Space* **58**, BF03351933 (2006).
 - [13] A. G. Wood, L. Alfonsi, L. B. N. Clausen, Y. Jin, L. Spogli, J. Urbář, J. T. Rawlings, I. C. Whittaker, G. D. Dorrian, P. Hoeg, D. Kotova, C. Cesaroni, A. Cicone, J. Miedzik, E. Gierlach, P. Kochańska, P. Wojtkiewicz, G. Shahtahmassebi, and W. J. Miloch, Variability of Ionospheric Plasma: Results from the ESA Swarm Mission, *Space Science Reviews* **218**, 52 (2022).
 - [14] M. F. Ivarsen, A. Lozinsky, J.-P. St-Maurice, A. Spicher, D. Huyghebaert, G. C. Hussey, D. Galeschuk, B. Pitzel, and J. Vierinen, The Distribution of Small-Scale Irregularities in the E-Region, and Its Tendency to Match the Spectrum of Field-Aligned Current Structures in the F-Region, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics* **128**, e2022JA031233 (2023).
 - [15] M. F. Ivarsen, M. D. Gillies, D. R. Huyghebaert, J.-P. St-Maurice, A. Lozinsky, D. Galeschuk, E. Donovan, and G. C. Hussey, Turbulence Embedded Into the Ionosphere by Electromagnetic Waves, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics* **129**, e2023JA032310 (2024).
 - [16] J. Park, H. Lühr, D. J. Knudsen, J. K. Burchill, and Y.-S. Kwak, Alfvén waves in the auroral region, their Poynting flux, and reflection coefficient as estimated from Swarm observations, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics* **122**, 2345 (2017).
 - [17] M. F. Ivarsen, J. Park, Y.-S. Kwak, Y. Jin, D. J. Knudsen, and L. B. N. Clausen, Observational Evidence for the Role of Hall Conductance in Alfvén Wave Reflection, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics* **125**, e2020JA028119 (2020).
 - [18] Y. Kazama, B.-J. Wang, S.-Y. Wang, P. T. P. Ho, S. W. Y. Tam, T.-F. Chang, C.-Y. Chiang, and K. Asamura, Low-energy particle experiments—electron analyzer (LEPe) onboard the Arase spacecraft, *Earth, Planets and Space* **69**, 165 (2017).
 - [19] S. Kasahara, S. Yokota, T. Mitani, K. Asamura, M. Hirahara, Y. Shibano, and T. Takashima, Medium-energy particle experiments—electron analyzer (MEP-e) for the exploration of energization and radiation in geospace (ERG) mission, *Earth, Planets and Space* **70**, 69 (2018).
 - [20] T. Mitani, T. Takashima, S. Kasahara, W. Miyake, and M. Hirahara, High-energy electron experiments (HEP) aboard the ERG (Arase) satellite, *Earth, Planets and Space* **70**, 77 (2018).
 - [21] Y. Miyoshi, I. Shinohara, T. Takashima, K. Asamura, N. Higashio, T. Mitani, S. Kasahara, S. Yokota, Y. Kazama, S.-Y. Wang, S. W. Y. Tam, P. T. P. Ho, Y. Kasahara, Y. Kasaba, S. Yagitani, A. Matsuoka, H. Kojima, Y. Katoh, K. Shiokawa, and K. Seki, Geospace exploration project ERG, *Earth, Planets and Space* **70**, 101 (2018).
 - [22] M. F. Ivarsen, Y. Miyashita, J.-P. St-Maurice, G. C. Hussey, B. Pitzel, D. Galeschuk, S. Marei, R. B. Horne, Y. Kasahara, S. Matsuda, S. Kasahara, K. Keika, Y. Miyoshi, K. Yamamoto, A. Shinbori, D. R. Huyghebaert, A. Matsuoka, S. Yokota, and F. Tsuchiya, Characteristic E-Region Plasma Signature of Magnetospheric Wave-Particle Interactions, *Physical Review Letters* **134**, 145201 (2025).
 - [23] B. H. La Rosa and D. L. Hysell, Modeling and Analysis of Artificial Periodic Inhomogeneities in the Ionosphere, *Radio Science* **60**, e2025RS008226 (2025).
 - [24] A. V. Gurevich, *Nonlinear Phenomena in the Ionosphere*, edited by J. G. Roeder and J. T. Wasson, *Physics and Chemistry in Space*, Vol. 10 (Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 1978).
 - [25] A. A. Tomko, A. J. Ferraro, and H. S. Lee, D region absorption effects during high-power radio wave heating, *Radio Science* **15**, 675 (1980).
 - [26] V. A. Yankovsky, K. V. Martyshenko, R. O. Manuilova, and A. G. Feofilov, Oxygen dayglow emissions as proxies for atomic oxygen and ozone in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere, *Journal of Molecular Spectroscopy New Visions of Spectroscopic Databases, Volume II*, **327**, 209 (2016).

- [27] V. Laporta, R. Celiberto, and J. Tennyson, Dissociative electron attachment and electron-impact resonant dissociation of vibrationally excited $\{\mathrm{O}\}_{-2}$ molecules, *Physical Review A* **91**, 012701 (2015).
- [28] P. D. Burrow, Dissociative attachment from the $\mathrm{O}_2(\mathrm{a}1\Delta\mathrm{g})$ state, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **59**, 4922 (1973).
- [29] A. S. Kirillov and V. B. Belakhovsky, The Kinetics of O_2 Singlet Electronic States in the Upper and Middle Atmosphere During Energetic Electron Precipitation, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* **126**, e2020JD033177 (2021).
- [30] A. Bouziane and M. Djebli, Direct ionization of metastable oxygen and nitrogen atoms in the Earth's upper atmosphere, *Advances in Space Research* **76**, 6975 (2025).